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Integrating SOEs with a methanation reactor for methane gas production using an MCFC for CO₂ capture from biogas

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Abstract

This study reports a concept of coupling two Solid Oxide Electrolysers (SOE) directly and indirectly with a methanation reactor for production of methane-rich gas for either an electricity or heat storage application on a larger scale. The main idea is focussed on increasing the ratio of methane in the biogas by removing CO₂ using an MCFC.

Water and biogas are used as the input to an SOE and an MCFC respectively. The SOE produces pure hydrogen gas, delivered to the MCFC anode. Biogas is supplied to the MCFC cathode. Here, the CO₂ is captured and transferred to the anode from where it passes to the methanation reactor together with the water formed from the hydrogen oxidation. The methane-rich gas from the MCFC cathode effluent and the methanation reactor output are sent to storage or fed into the natural gas grid as pure methane. Pure Oxygen is released from the first SOE anode and will be mixed with the biogas input to the MCFC to supply the oxidant to the MCFC reaction. In this way, close control is kept of the reactant gas flow compositions.

On 'discharging' the gas storage by extracting methane from the gas grid and feeding this to the SOFC, the second SOE will be fed with the SOFC anode effluent composed mainly of CO₂ and H₂O. This in turn delivers synthetic gas (CO + H₂) for the methanation reactor. It is necessary to have a control over the admissible H₂/CO ratio of 1:3 which is optimal for methane production in the methanation reactor. The concept requires detailed electrochemical, chemical and thermal simulations.

Introduction

The global generation of power from renewable energy sources continued to be on the increase (i.e. 71 mtoe) reaching about 14.5% of the 2017 record-breaking increase, which are responsible for a third of the net growth in power generation in 2018. A Large portion of the growth was achieved mainly by energy from wind and solar [1]. These trends are more than likely to continue in the future. Power produced from renewable energy sources such as wind and solar, however, mismatches the world electrical energy demand due to its fluctuating availability and nature. With the growth in renewable energy investments observed in recent times, proposing mitigation ideas to the inherent issues with the future energy infrastructure become increasingly necessary [2], [3].

The key issues are power fluctuation, flexibility of the system and the efficiencies. There is a need to systematically store the excess energy available in peak power production periods in compensative measures against the lower energy production periods in order to aid the scale-up of employability of energy from renewables [4]. As such, energy storage is considered a key technology as it can help provide an assuagement for the inherent deficiencies and inefficiencies when fully integrated with the existing electrical power grid [5], [6]. Various energy storage technologies based on their working principles are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Energy storage techniques

Energy Form	Principles	Ref
Electrical	Superconducting magnetic energy storage (SMES), super-capacitors.	[7]
Mechanical	Flywheels, pumped storage and compressed air.	[8]
Thermal	Thermochemical, sensible heat and latent heat	[9], [10]
Chemical	Electrochemical, power-to-liquid/gas (P2L, P2G, P2X)	[11]–[13]

Asides the working principles, the techniques also differ in further aspects, such as mode of discharge, time requirement for start-up, capacity, operating conditions, bulkiness of the equipment involved, and efficiencies, involving the application of various disciplines to overcome the technical issues [14].

Energy storage by SMES, flywheels and super capacitors offer some advantages over the other storage technologies which includes high round-trip efficiency, low charging and response time, long life cycle, and high power density. However, the major drawback of SMES and super capacitor is the cost of installation in comparison with the storage capacity [15], while flywheels are affected by standby losses. Both flywheel and super capacitor suffer from low energy density [16].

Pumped hydro power energy storage has the capability of high energy storage duration (for over 6 months) but still contributes to the emission of greenhouse gasses due to the released of CO₂ from cement production during construction [16]. The major disadvantages of compressed air energy storage (CAES) are the dependence on geological formation and high installation cost [17].

The use of batteries for energy storage enjoin low maintenance requirement and high round trip efficiency, but lacks high energy capacity and density and has an issue of self-discharge. Therefore limiting their utilisation to short term storage [11].

Easy transportation of energy to where it is needed is another topic of interest and the necessities to store excess renewable energy cannot be overemphasised. High energy and power density, utilisable for extended period of time can be achieved by employing power-to-fuel technologies [14].

In regions, where there is abundant solar or wind energy sources, one profound way to store excess energy is to employ the concept of Power-to-Methane (P2M) [18], and

integrate it with high temperature fuel cells such as molten carbonate fuel cell (MCFC) and solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) in such a way as to exploit the stored renewable energy. A P2M plant basically consists of a water electrolyser, a CO₂ source, and a methanation module as shown in Figure 1 [19].

Figure 1: Principle of power-to-methane

Pure hydrogen gas is produced by the electrolyser from water and sent to the methanator. In the methanation unit, the pure hydrogen gas is reacted with CO₂ to generate a mixture of gasses which primarily consist of methane and steam [18]. The reaction equations are presented in Eqn. (10) - (12). The methane gas obtained can be sent to storage, or fed into the natural gas grid as pure methane to be later used, for example in SOFCs for power generation. Methane fuel is preferred because of its relatively higher hydrogen to carbon ratio compared to other hydrocarbon fuels [20].

CO₂ sources for the technology can include biomass plants (i.e. from biogas upgrading - approximately 100% (v/v) [21]), power generation plants (i.e. from combustion of coal - about 10-15% (v/v) [22], natural gas - about 3-5% (v/v), petroleum - about 3-8% (v/v), industrial processes (i.e. in the production of cement - about 14-33% (v/v) [23], production of ethylene oxide - approximately 100% (v/v), production of Iron and steel - about 20-30% (v/v) [23]) and ambient air - approximately 0.04% (v/v) [24].

The technical feasibility of CO₂ capture from these sectors is positive, however, the integration in the present technology is economically dependent on the CO₂ partial pressures in the exhaust gas due to the energetic and procedural effort for separation [23]. Common CO₂ sources, investigated in past studies are those from the combustion of coal, natural gas or petroleum. Their integration with fuel cell plants particularly SOFCs is a breakthrough in achieving concurrently a huge fuel conversion efficiency and very low pollutants emission [25]. This however eliminate the problem of transporting CO₂ to the site. Nevertheless, the energy requirement for the CO₂ separation still makes it somewhat less energy-efficient. Therefore, the incorporation of a molten carbonate fuel cell (MCFC) as the CO₂ separation unit could make the overall plant an energy-efficient one.

1. Literature Review

Many institutions and research institutes are geared towards the development of such technology i.e. integrated gasification fuel cell cycle (IGFC) that utilizes a low cost fuel to generate electricity with high efficiency and the annihilation of emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) or the incorporation of a carbon capture technology. One typical advantage of this concept is the electrochemical oxidation of the fuel that occur in the fuel cell, thereby leaving only CO₂ and H₂O as the exhaust unlike the combustion engines which leaves oxides of sulphur and nitrogen in the exhaust. Several thermodynamic studies of gas turbines and fuel cells (especially SOFCs and MCFCs) integration to form hybrid FC-GT cycle have been reported in literature in the last decades. Examples of such studies are concisely presented below.

Ghosh and De (2003) carried out a study on thermodynamic performance of a 20 MW_e IGFC system. The configuration included a gasifier through which oxygen was constantly

supplied, an air separating unit (ASU) and a slurry feed. A syngas purifier with the operating temperature of 673.2K was used for the initial removal of sulphur-containing compounds and particulates before being sent into the fuel cell. The authors reported 48 to 55% lower heating value (LHV) efficiencies, varying with the ratio of cycle pressure (i.e. 5 to 35) and cell potentials (i.e. 0.91 to 0.965V).

Kivisaari et al. (2004) carried out a feasibility study on a high temperature SOFC plant integrated with a coal gasifier. The group assessed a 30 MWe system operating on a dry coal feed, and oxygen blown gasifier to produce syngas. The exhaust gas from the SOFC was used to reheat the syngas after being quenched. The study revealed 43% LHV efficiency without SOFC anode gas recirculation, and 47% LHV efficiency with SOFC anode gas recirculation while assuming a cell voltage of 0.725V at fuel utilisation of 85%.

Verma, Rao, and Samuelsen (2006) reported a sensitivity analysis of a Vision 21 350 MWe coal power plant with CO₂ capture. The plant's configuration included a fluidised bed gasifier, a methanator, an ASU, WGS reactors, a membrane-based H₂ separator, a catalytic combustor, a heat recovery unit, a CO₂ compressor and a SOFC fed with methane and recirculated H₂. The authors reported 51 to 53% LHV efficiency, while assuming 85% fuel utilisation, 0.75V cell potential and an operating pressure ranging from 5.9 to 19.7 atm after optimising the parameters.

Romano et al. (2009) studied a coal gasifier integrated with an SOFC plant with the capacity of 590 MWe. The SOFC plant was fed with a syngas produced from the coal gasifier, and highly pressurised air produced by the gas turbine compressor. The study gave approximately 59% LHV efficiency while maintaining a fuel utilisation of 85%, cell voltage of 0.753V in the SOFC, with and without syngas expander, and a pressure ratio of 20 to 26.5 respectively. The plant configuration assessed could be improved by addition of units like methanation, or CO₂ capture to achieve even higher efficiencies passing the 60% limit.

Spallina et al. (2011) thermodynamically analysed an SOFC-based plant with Carbon capture. Herein, an air separator was used to produce pure oxygen feed for the gasification of coal. Syngas produced is passed directly to SOFC modules after being cleaned and passing through heat recovery. The remaining combustible gas from the SOFC's anode exhaust were combusted with the pure O₂ produced in the ASU, the product gas was used to generate steam by heat recovery before condensing and compressing the water and carbon dioxide (cryogenic separation), respectively. The author fed the coal with the captured CO₂ in the lock hoppers thereby avoiding the use of N₂ in order to achieve high CO₂ purity. Nevertheless, the study of the 520MW_e plant showed 47% LHV efficiency, and approximately 0.0211 kg/kWh emission of carbon dioxide while maintaining 89% and 0.747V of fuel utilisation and cell potential, respectively in the SOFC. Though, the study achieved reduced CO₂ emissions, the amount released will however increase over time and the assessed plant did not cater for its reabsorption back to the cycle.

Romano, Spallina, and Campanari (2011) also thermodynamically studied an SOFC-based IGFC (fuelled with coal) plant integrated with H₂ post firing, physical absorption carbon capture, and a methanator. The plant assessed gave 53% LHV efficiency and specific CO₂ emission of 30.9% for a 582 MW_e system while maintaining 74% fuel utilisation, and a cell potential of 0.812V in the SOFC module. Though a better CO₂ management with respect to net power was achieved with the configuration, the high complexity of the plant incurred high cost of the equipment required.

This study intends to report a concept of coupling two Solid Oxide Electrolysers (SOE) directly and indirectly with a methanation reactor for production of methane-rich gas for either an electricity or heat storage application on a larger scale. The main idea is focussed on this biogas upgrading by removing CO₂ using an MCFC. The plant will be

thermodynamically assessed, and a parametric sensitivity analysis will be carried out as regards to the overall efficiency.

2. Design of MCFC CO₂ capture plant layout

Figure 2 depicts the overall plant layout for a system using biogas input and CO₂ recycling via an MCFC unit. Water and biogas are used as the input to an SOE and an MCFC, respectively, as shown in the flow chart. The SOE produces pure hydrogen gas, delivered to the MCFC anode. Biogas is supplied to the MCFC cathode. Here, the CO₂ is transferred to the anode by facilitating the oxygen ion diffusion necessary for the hydrogen oxidation reaction. From where it passes to the methanation reactor together with the water formed from the hydrogen oxidation. The methane enriched gas from the MCFC cathode effluent and the methanation reactor output are sent to storage or fed into the natural gas grid as pure methane. Pure Oxygen is released from the first SOE anode (air electrode) and will be mixed with the biogas input to the MCFC cathode to supply the oxidant to the MCFC reaction. In this way, close control is kept of the reactant gas flow compositions.

On 'discharging' the gas storage by extracting methane from the gas grid and feeding this to the SOFC, the second SOE will be fed with the SOFC anode effluent composed mainly of CO₂ and H₂O. This in turn delivers syn gas (CO + H₂) for the methanation reactor. It is necessary to have a control over the admissible H₂/CO ratio of 1:3 which is an optimal ratio for production of methane in the methanator.

Explanations of reactions taking place in each unit and their significances in the configuration are discussed in the succeeding sections.

Figure 2: Proposed plant layout

The SOE

The first step as shown in Figure 2 is the co-electrolysis of water by the solid oxide electrolyser-1 (SOE₁), which can use power derived from excess renewable energy sources i.e. solar and wind energy to split water (H₂O) into hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂) [44]. A mixture of CO₂ and H₂O is processed in SOE₂ as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3 shows the principle of SOEs. H₂ (as in the case of SOE₁) and / or CO (as in the case of SOE₂) evolves from the cathode of the SOE (i.e. the fuel electrode) while O₂ evolves from the anode (the 'air' or 'oxygen' electrode). A solid electrolyte separates the two electrodes is conductive only for oxygen ions (O²⁻). The input gas stream for SOE₁ is composed of H₂O (steam) while for SOE₂, it includes both carbon dioxide and steam. Here, the feed gas would have access to the electrons delivered from the excess solar and wind power to produce either H₂ gas (in SOE₁ which delivers to the MCFC anode in Figure 2) or syngas (H₂ and CO) (in SOE₂ which delivers to the methanation unit) as well as the oxygen ions according to Eqn. (1) and (2) [45].

Figure 3: Schematic illustration of an SOEC

The oxygen ions are transported through the solid electrolyte to the anode where they are oxidized to oxygen gas as shown in Eqn. (3) and sent to either the MCFC cathode (as in SOE₁) or storage tank (as in SOE₂) which can later be used in the SOFC.

There is complexity in the SOEs co-electrolysis of the mixture of steam and carbon dioxide compared to individual electrolysis of the feed in SOEs. This is due to the following possible reactions represented in Eqn. (4) to (7) which could occur on the cathode [46]:

The high-temperature steam electrolysis (SOE) offers the benefit of a lower electric energy demand compared to low-temperature electrolyzers (Alkaline and PEM), especially if the latent heat of water vaporisation is provided from an external source. Several studies in the literature ascertained that the electrolysis of steam at temperature of 1173.2K requires approximately 20% lower electrical energy than electrolysis of water at 353.2K. This high-temperature steam demand, however, aids the thermal integration with the methanation reactor and therefore reduces the need for additional cooling devices. Therefore, SOEs are promising technology for this purpose, albeit the effect of high temperature and long term operation on the integrity of the ceramic materials is questionable [47].

Molten carbonate fuel cell

This study proposes to use a Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell for supplying CO₂ captured from biogas to the methanation reactor. This solution gives pure CO₂ delivered directly to the reaction zone. The MCFC can at the same time be used to upgrade biogas through the removal of CO₂.

In general principle, an MCFC uses CO₃²⁻ as electron carrier through its molten carbonate electrolyte. When CO₂ gas is supplied to the MCFC cathode, it reacts with O₂ to form CO₃²⁻ which then diffuses to the MCFC anode where it is recovered as CO₂ again after reacting with a molecule of H₂ with the generation of two moles of electrons as shown in Eqn. (8) and (9).

In other words, MFCs can act as a gas filter which if employed in the present study for removing CO₂ from biogas, can help improve the heating value of the biogas and as well supply free CO₂ (i.e. nearly zero energy cost) for the methanation reaction.

Methanation unit

The syngas produced via the co-electrolysis of steam and CO₂ could as well be fed directly to the SOFC anode, instead of CH₄ but several studies [29], [30], [48] revealed low fuel conversion efficiencies and high rate of air flow requirement for cooling the SOFC device when pure syngas is used as the fuel gas.

However, if a fraction or the whole fuel gas is made up of CH₄, internal reforming of the CH₄ gas will be enhanced by the heat generated within the SOFC electrochemical reaction, this in turn causing cooling of the device. Therefore, more coolant like air would be required when fuel gas with zero percent methane is used which consequently reduces the efficiency of the fuel cell [29].

Methanation is an exothermic reaction [44] as shown in the following chemical equations (10) to (12) with the reactor temperature ranging from 503 to 1023K and the process pressures ranging from 4.4 to 84 atm [49].

Thermodynamically, the reactions are favoured at low temperatures and high pressures.

The important criteria for designing an efficient methanator are listed as follows [50]:

- (i) Operate at conditions that aid high methane yield and fast kinetics,
- (ii) Avoid catalyst deactivation caused by sulphur poisoning.
- (iii) Avoid conditions such as extremely low temperature or inadequate H₂:CO ratio which can deactivate the catalyst by deposition of carbon and formation of Nickel tetra carbonyl (Ni(CO)₄).
- (iv) Avoid sintering of catalysts at high temperature.

Considering the exothermic nature of the methanation reaction, the temperature conditions would appear difficult to achieve [50]. Nevertheless, addition of Steam could help increase the H₂ and O₂ content of the feed syngas, thereby, lowering the risk of carbon deposition.

The SOFC

Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) are high temperature (i.e. 500 to 900 °C) fuel-to-power devices [51] which accept directly not only hydrogen, but also hydrocarbons [52] such as CH₄, C₂H₅OH [53], C₃H₈ [54], [55], or reformed CO(NH₂)₂ [56] as fuel for generation of power. Syngas (CO, H₂) and ammonia (NH₃) are also potential fuels.

The SOFC will be fed with the gas stream generated at the methanation unit which consist mainly of CH₄ and steam together with some percentage of unreacted CO, H₂ and even CO₂. SOFC can internally reform the methane gas as shown in Eqn. (13), (14) and (15) [57] which practically overcomes the requirement for an external fuel reforming unit. External reforming will increase the cost and makes the operation complex, or could also reduce the plant's efficiencies [20].

The internal fuel reforming reactions represented in Eqn. (13) and (15) is enhanced by the heat generated by the electrochemical oxidation reactions of the fuel at the anode. However, in a typical SOFC operating condition, heat generated by the electrochemical reaction is higher than the heat required for the internal reforming reaction. This thereby still requires additional external cooling of the device but would have been lowered by 50% as compared to that required if external reforming reaction is used.

However, this mismatch in heat requirement and supply could give lead to non-uniformity in temperature distribution within the SOFC device which consequently could induced thermal stress on the cells and cause mechanical failure. Nevertheless, the above stated problem can be attenuated through the addition of little amount of O₂ to the feed fuel (i.e. CH₄) [58]. Product gas from the SOFC will be recycled by means of a blower and cooling the stream might not be necessary since high-temperature steam electrolysis (SOE) is employed.

Mole balance of the proposed plant

The mole balance of the proposed plant was carried out using the Aspen PlusTM as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Mole balance of the MCFC CO₂ capture plant in Aspen Plus

1 mol/hr of water is fed into the SOE1 cathode and biogas containing 1 mol/hr of CH₄ and CO₂ each respectively is fed into the MCFC cathode. The stoichiometric chemical reactions elucidated in the preceding sections for each module were employed for the calculations.

3. Results

Table 2 shows the mole balance of the MCFC CO₂ capture plant. According to the performed analysis, the total number of electrons spent and generated are 20 and 28 respectively. It is worth to note that the extra 8 electrons generated is as a result of the 1 mol/hr of CH₄ captured form the biogas by the MCFC. It is assumed that Oxygen as oxidant for both MCFC and SOFC is abundantly available for the calculations.

Mole flows												
Stream Name	Feed-H ₂ O	SOE1-out	Biogas	MCFC-Anode-out	MCFC-Cathode-out	MCFC-SOE2	Storage	SOFC-in	SOFC-out	SOE2-in	SOE2-Cathode-out	
H ₂ O	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	6	6	0	
H ₂		1	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	6	

CO ₂	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	4	4	0
CH ₄	0	1	0	1	0	2	3	0	0	0
CO	0	0	0	0	4	2	2	2	0	4

Table 2: Mole balance of the MCFC CO₂ capture plant

4. Conclusion

The study presents a concept of coupling SOEs with a MCFC and methanation reactor for an electricity storage application on a larger scale. The concept seems attractive as it includes storage of excess renewable energy, CO₂ capture, and temperature compatibility with methanation reactions and higher round trip efficiency as observed from the result. Detailed investigations based on mathematical modelling, thermodynamics and experiments will be conducted in the next step of research.

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